

FATIGUE LIFE ASSESSMENT OF INJECTION-MOLDED REINFORCED SHORT FIBRE THERMOPLASTICS: NOTCH EFFECTS

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1 Introduction

The automotive industry needs to reduce the weight of vehicles for environmental and economical purposes. One expected way to reach this goal is to use reinforced thermoplastics for the design of mechanical structures because of their high ratio “fatigue strength / density” compared with metallic materials. During its life, each automotive component can be submitted to repeated loadings with variable amplitude. As in service failures must be avoided, fatigue characterization is necessary to optimize the design of thermoplastic parts.

A specific methodology for multiaxial fatigue life assessment of injection-molded components was previously proposed to this aim [1]. The latter, called ‘Through Process Modelling’ (TPM), allows linking the injection process simulation to the fatigue life assessment with a fatigue criterion, through the estimate of heterogeneous local anisotropic properties due to variable fibre orientation. One of the major advantages of such an approach is to account for microstructure orientation influence, due to injection process, on fatigue life. The relevance of the TPM has been discussed by using as a reference a large multiaxial fatigue database for PBT-PET GF30 and PA66 GF35 involving in each case different type of injection-molded samples and various fatigue loadings (tension, torsion, combined tension-torsion, pure shear with two load ratios). Very good results were obtained for both materials with an energetic fatigue criterion using only one S-N line for the identification.

For further correct employment of the TPM in the case of industrial parts for which the complexity of the geometry and induced microstructure may generate important stress-strain gradients, notably in the plane of the part, it is first essential to evaluate the TPM for injected notched specimens. This is the aim of the present paper with special attention paid on the following open issue: how to compute the equivalent mechanical property required by the fatigue criterion in the presence of high stress-strain gradients?

2 Injection-molded notched samples and fatigue tests

The studied material is PA6 GF30, (Polyamide 6 with 30% mass short glass fibres). Notched samples have been injection-molded using two different injection gates (longitudinal and side) as depicted in Fig. 1. In each case, three different notch radius values are considered: 0.5 mm, 1 mm and 2 mm. The parameter wall thickness is 3.2 mm for all specimens. All specimens are conditioned using standard conditions of 23°C and 50% relative humidity.

Every type of notched specimens is submitted to tensile fatigue tests with a load ratio of $R=0.1$. The tests are force controlled and the signal wave force is sinusoidal. The frequency is 4 Hz. Results allow checking the respective influences of the notch severity and of the injection direction on the fatigue life in these loading conditions, and establishing a first database for the evaluation of the TPM in the presence of local field concentrations.

3 Through Process Modelling

3.1 Short description of the original version

Fig. 1 presents the methodology as proposed by [1] for injected components. From the geometry of the part (1), the process simulation with Moldflow® is performed (2) and provides the fibre orientation tensor at each point of the part. The following step (3) uses the orientation tensor in order to estimate (with Digimat®) local effective properties and then compute (with Abaqus®) the stress-strain response as a function of local anisotropy. Mechanical fields thus obtained as a function of fibre orientation are used as input data for the application of a fatigue criterion in the last step (4). In such a methodology, the fatigue criterion to be used and the way to compute this criterion have to be chosen by the user. For the first application of the TPM to un-notched samples, mechanical fields were averaged over the thickness of each shell element and the criterion applied for each element. The fatigue life of the sample was the lowest one observed over all the elements. Different fatigue criteria using only one S-N line for the identification were compared. The energetic criterion due to [2] was shown to give very good results.

3.1 Improvement for notched samples and evaluation

In the present work dealing with the TPM application to notched specimens, the energetic criterion due to [2] is maintained. Nevertheless, if the averaging process over the thickness of each element was relevant for un-notched specimens for which mechanical field gradient was mainly due to the variation of the microstructure in the thickness, the presence of the notch induces field gradients both in the plane and in the thickness of the samples. As a consequence, a specific volume averaging process of mechanical fields taking into account both types of gradients (in the plane and in the thickness) is proposed. The simulated fatigue lives resulting from the TPM with both averaging processes (previous and new ones) are compared to the experimental fatigue lives showing the efficiency of the new way to compute the criterion. The results mark a meaningful step allowing envisioning the application of the TPM to industrial parts as a short prospect.

Moreover, the observation of the profiles of the orientation tensor resulting from the process simulation (for each notch radius and injection direction) allows a better understanding of the origins of the field gradients (influences of the severity of the notch for a given injection direction and of the microstructure orientation for a given notch radius). This allows progressing in the analysis of the experimental fatigue lives in the presence of gradient effects.

Fig. 1 Injected notched samples (left), Through Process Modelling (TPM) by [1] (right).

References

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